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ENLIGHT RISE- RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA WITH AND FOR SOCIETY: LEVERAGING DIGITAL INNOVATION FOR A GREENER AND HEALTHIER EUROPE

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Description (short)
The deliverable D2.2 presents the ENLIGHT Research & Innovation Observatory. It is a comprehensive platform presenting the research and innovation capacities and synergies' areas of the ENLIGHT universities. It also gathers a variety of R&I outputs and results from the Alliance. The R&I Observatory is available at this link https://observatory.enlight-eu.org

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INTRODUCTION

ENLIGHT and ENLIGHT RISE

ENLIGHT is a European university alliance willing to promote equitable quality of life, sustainability and global engagement through higher education transformation. ENLIGHT brings together nine comprehensive research-intensive universities from nine European countries (University of the Basque Country, University of Bordeaux, Comenius University Bratislava, University of Galway, Ghent University, University of Göttingen, University of Groningen, University of Tartu, Uppsala University). ENLIGHT has obtained funding from the European Commission in the framework of the Horizon 2020 Science with and for Society (SwafS) work programme.

The ENLIGHT RISE project (Research and Innovation agenda with and for SociEty) seeks to strengthen the research and innovation dimension of the ENLIGHT alliance. In synergy with ENLIGHT's educational components and surrounding ecosystems, ENLIGHT RISE will deploy a comprehensive joint transformation agenda for our universities.

The ENLIGHT RISE project is structured around nine major Work Packages.

The main objective of Work Package 2 (WP2) of ENLIGHT RISE is to create synergies through R&I capacity building and to contribute to establish a common Research & Innovation agenda. Complementing the mapping of expertise in the ENLIGHT Think Tank (Erasmus+), WP2 analyses the alliance members' scientific and technological profiles to identify the strongest research synergies leading to maximize ENLIGHT alliance's competitive advantage (task 2.1). WP2 Research & Innovation observatory will help identifying ENLIGHT R&I capacities (task 2.2) and R&I synergies will be established through focus groups and incentives mechanisms (task 2.3).

The ENLIGHT RISE Research & Innovation Observatory

This document represents deliverable D2.2, related to the Task 2.2 "Set up an ENLIGHT R&I Observatory".

The ENLIGHT R&I Observatory will be a key tool for designing a dynamic common Research & Innovation agenda with and for society. It will be a central resource for the ENLIGHT R&I-SG, the Think Tank, Living Labs, and Regional Academies to identify emerging topics and generate cross-disciplinary, relevant research synergies in a competitive way.

The R&I observatory will be strongly linked to the ENLIGHT website as well as to all the other ENLIGHT RISE Work Packages.

This document is organized in two main chapters:

1. The first section describes the process leading to the R&I Observatory set-up, the generation of content and it includes the development of the web-based tool.
2. The second section presents the ENLIGHT R&I Observatory and its different pages.

1. THE PROCESS

WP2 first launched the task T2.2 “Set up an ENLIGHT R&I observatory” by a survey and a brainstorm on what should be the ENLIGHT R&I Observatory. It was necessary to clarify what were the gap needs, the R&I Observatory added value, and to agree on a common definition.

Each university through its WP2 representatives was invited to fill in a questionnaire (appendix 1) to provide feedback on its expertise on observatories and expectations regarding the ENLIGHT R&I observatory.

This survey served as a basis for a WP2 brainstorm meeting on the R&I observatory in January 2022.

Following the brainstorm meeting, the definition of the ENLIGHT R&I Observatory was clarified:

“The ENLIGHT RISE R&I Observatory will be a one stop shop portal serving as resource centre for ENLIGHT RISE WPs’ results in order to identify synergies among consortium partners and with external stakeholders. It shall be a web interface with high storage capacity connected to the ENLIGHT website and containing a restricted access area for ENLIGHT RISE partners with secure repository and collaborative workspace. An interactive section shall be open to external ENLIGHT RISE stakeholders.”

We came to the conclusion that the R&I observatory could have different dimensions, its extension being dependent on time and budget constraints.

It was quickly noted we would need more time to get the R&I Observatory set up (definition of the tool, content, work with subcontractor, deliverable 2.1 finalised). We thus required to the EC a delay for the delivery of the web-based tool to have the ENLIGHT R&I Observatory operational by end of December 2022 (M16) instead of July 2022 (M11).

1.1. Content Development

We defined the objectives and identified what should be the future uses of the tool.

Objectives

- To facilitate the creation of a common R&I agenda for the ENLIGHT alliance
- To facilitate the identification of expertise of ENLIGHT partners on the flagship areas
- To facilitate the identification of synergies among ENLIGHT partners and with external stakeholders on the flagship areas.
- To present evolution of existing and future collaborations among ENLIGHT researchers and with external stakeholders.
- To access to the ENLIGHT WPs results

Future uses

The Research and Innovation Observatory will be a platform to foster the exchange, mutual learning and collaboration among ENLIGHT partners and external stakeholders. It will be a resource centre / catalogue to store and classify information to better identify the research and innovation profiles of ENLIGHT partners and their synergies. Finally, it will serve as showcase for external partners and funding institutions.

Figure 1 – Expectations for the ENLIGHT R&I observatory (Gitmind)

In order to define better the content of the tool, we identified our target groups and worked on users' stories.

For ENLIGHT researchers

Figure 2 - User stories for ENLIGHT Researchers (GitMind)

For Alliance partners

Figure 3 - User stories for Alliance Partners (GitMind)

For random visitors

Figure 4 - User stories for random visitors (GitMind)

The preparatory work enabled to state what is in the observatory and what it is not.

What is in the R&I Observatory

- Information on **what is ENLIGHT** and the **aim of the observatory** (as published in the *Enlight website*)
- **Short mapping of scientific and technological profiles of ENLIGHT universities**
 - Global vision on the interactions (thematic/network) of the profiles / static
- **Search per key word (already fixed) or institution to get information on the research expertise available at ENLIGHT universities (ideal tool/solution)**
- **Surveys and benchmark reports of RISE such as :**
 - digital infrastructure mapping report
 - map of DI/AI initiatives tools and methods in ENLIGHT
 - recommendation on research assessment systems
 - map of academy-industry partnerships
 - map and benchmarking report of existing initiatives supporting academy-industry collaborations and entrepreneurship
- **Existing initiatives of collaborations (based on the short mapping)**

What the R&I Observatory is not

- **ENLIGHT RISE Website**
- **Private repository space (SharePoint)**
- **Specific information related to the operational management of ENLIGHT RISE (management handbook, communication plan...)** (Sharepoint)
- **Information on the services offered by the R&I SG (ENLIGHT website)**
- **Same information as already available in the ENLIGHT website. (ENLIGHT website)**
- **Request for partner search (ENLIGHT website)**
- **Information on financial incentives (prizes/seed funding) /calls for proposals (ENLIGHT website)**
- **Action plan focus group (ENLIGHT website)**
- **Interactive forum with external stakeholders (not realistic in terms of HR and finance)**

We agreed that having repository on research capacity on the flagship areas at each partner was clue as making visible research capacities could facilitate connections among ENLIGHT researchers and stakeholders.

Taking into account that ENLIGHT RISE had tools serving as secure repository and collaborative workshop (ENLIGHT RISE Sharepoint), a restricted access area for ENLIGHT partners would not be included in the observatory. As for the interactive section open to external stakeholders, this was not possible due to time and budget constraints and it will be considered as a possible future development of the tool.

1.2. R&I Observatory structure and proposal of contents

Thanks to all these previous steps, we elaborated a general structure of the ENLIGHT R&I observatory.

Figure 5 – Structure of the web-based tool (Gitmind)

The structure is composed of four main sections:

1. Home page to inform on what is the R&I observatory
2. ENLIGHT R&I expertise; giving the possibility to search partners' R&I capacities using different filter options
3. Global vision of collaborations, based on the main results of the mapping task of ENLIGHT universities' scientific and technological profiles (deliverable D2.1)
4. ENLIGHT outputs: surveys and benchmark reports of ENLIGHT RISE

We have adopted a step-by-step approach for the section related to R&I expertise to be able to collect the data needed by the timeline defined for the deliverable.

We started with a pilot phase with four universities (University of the Basque Country, University of Bordeaux, Ghent University and University of Tartu). The remaining universities will be able to provide their data to be integrated within the observatory in 2023.

The “pilot” universities were asked to fill in a table related to their research units (name, description, expertise, subthematics, key words, ENLIGHT flagships) (see appendix 2).

In order to have the same fields of expertise/scientific topics as reference, we decided to use the list of ERC Panels for ERC calls 2021 and 2022 (see appendix 3), being a European reference and classification that could be understood by each university.

Once one main thematic (ERC panel reference) is identified, subthematics (related to the panel chosen) can be selected.

External development of the web-based tool

As stated in the Grant Agreement, the development of the web-based tool ENLIGHT R&I Observatory was executed by a subcontractor (web interface with high storage capacity).

Following all these previous steps, we wrote the specifications to be sent to potential subcontractors.

In July 2022, the lead beneficiary of the task (University of Bordeaux) contracted with a company.

We agreed on a timeline with three main phases (zoning/design; development; test) before the validation to make the website online. We set up a steering group to work with the subcontractor. The steering group was composed by five persons from the lead and co-leads institutions of WP2 and was in charge of providing the content of the tool and validating the different steps/phases of implementation of the R&I Observatory. A member of the ENLIGHT communication group participated also in the steering committee to make sure it was in line with the ENLIGHT dissemination and communication strategy and guidelines.

• Area of Responsibilities per organisation

The work with the subcontractor started on September 1st, 2022. We exchanged on a regular basis (emails/meetings/phone) with the company.

Work with communication group

In terms of design, we took as reference the ENLIGHT Brand Book and ENLIGHT Dissemination and Communication Strategy.

Benefiting from the experience and work done by the ENLIGHT RISE WP8 team on the web-based repository on research impact, it was indicated not to include in the R&I observatory any general information related to the ENLIGHT Alliance being already part of the ENLIGHT website. The objective is that the Observatory is seen as an integral part of the general ENLIGHT website.

2. The ENLIGHT Research & Innovation Observatory

Chapter 2 presents the contents of the ENLIGHT R&I observatory as published on the 14th of December 2022.

For some sections, this website will be updated on a regular basis, notably for the pages related to the ENLIGHT R&I expertise (to include all partners' R&I expertise) and to the ENLIGHT outputs (to be published as soon as they become available). We plan to update the data of the research expertise at least once a year.

2.1. Home page

The home page is the page users get first access to, through the ENLIGHT website or other web platforms where the link to the ENLIGHT R&I observatory is provided.

This page is composed by a general introduction of what the R&I observatory is, the aim and the content of the online tool. Some key figures are also highlighted.

At the end of the page, users will have the opportunity to contact the ENLIGHT R&I Observatory team (generic email address).

From this page users will access the different sections of the online tool:

1. ENLIGHT Scientific profile
2. ENLIGHT Research & Innovation expertise
3. ENLIGHT Outputs

2.2. ENLIGHT Scientific Profile

On this page, users will be able to access to the main results of the mapping of scientific and technological profile of the ENLIGHT Alliance and as well to the individual profiles of each university realised through the WP2 Task 2.1 – deliverable D2.1.

Note: You will have access first to the scientific and technological profile of the ENLIGHT Alliance. Interested in the individual profile of each university, below you can get more information.

Collected data for ENLIGHT Universities

Number of collected FamPat, SciPub and ResPro data for each ENLIGHT university

ENLIGHT UNIVERSITIES	Number of collected FamPat	Number of collected SciPub	Number of collected ResPro
1 University of the Basque Country	150	21,200	231
2 University of Bordeaux	480	23,557	208
3 Comenius University Bratislava	113	2,795	57
4 University of Galway	260	9,787	338
5 Ghent University	1,219	73,309	644
6 University of Göttingen	260	24,543	244
7 University of Groningen	225	26,456	404
8 University of Tartu	96	6,381	283
9 Uppsala University	7	46,807	538

FamPat and SciPub data collected via Lens.org | ResPro data collected via CORIS

Source: LENS.ORG | CORIS | Research - Science and Ingeg - Created with Datawrapper

ENLIGHT Scientific and Technological Profile

Temporal distribution for collected FamPat for all ENLIGHT Univ.

Number of collected FamPat per earliest priority date for all ENLIGHT Universities

FamPat data collected via LENS.ORG
Download image - Created with Datawrapper

Temporal distribution for collected SciPub for all ENLIGHT Univ.

Number of collected SciPub per publication date for all ENLIGHT Universities

SciPub data collected via LENS.ORG - 2016 - 2021 - Scientific articles
Download image - Created with Datawrapper

Temporal distribution for collected ResPro for all ENLIGHT Univ.

Number of collected ResPro per starting date for all ENLIGHT Universities

ResPro data collected via CORDIS - FFP7 + H2020 - 2007 - 2022
Download image - Created with Datawrapper

Collection, processing and analysis of specific scientific & technological data related to the nine ENLIGHT universities provides an understanding of the R&I activities of the ENLIGHT Alliance and allows similarities between the ENLIGHT universities: R&I topic similarities and existing partnerships in order to facilitate the identification of potential collaboration areas.

In order to identify areas where ENLIGHT has strong R&I capacity, we rely on the grid provided by the 17 Sustainable Goals Development – SDG (reliable and readable blueprint to understand and characterize scientific data and link them to the ENLIGHT flagship domains).

The mapping helped us identify similarity in terms of topic.

Overview of ENLIGHT R&I Partner's Network

We have identified the R&I partners our ENLIGHT universities collaborate with, including both non-for-profit and for-profit organisations.

• For-Profit Organisations / • Non-For-Profit Organisations

ENLIGHT collaboration network based on Family Patents (GEPHI)

*One university is not represented due to specific rules related to the attribution of patents

■ For-Profit Organisations / ■ Non-For-Profit Organisations

ENLIGHT collaboration network based on Research Projects (GEPHI)

For further details, the full mapping of the research and innovation capacities of the Enlight Alliance is available [here](#)

University Profiles

University of the Basque Country	See details
University of Bordeaux	See details
Comenius University Bratislava	See details
University of Galway	See details
Ghent University	See details
University of Göttingen	See details
University of Groningen	See details
University of Tartu	See details
Uppsala University	See details

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2.3. ENLIGHT R&I Expertise

As outlined before, having a repository on research capacities of the ENLIGHT universities would facilitate the connections among ENLIGHT researchers and stakeholders. We dedicated one section of the tool to the possibility to look for expertise/capacities available within the ENLIGHT alliance.

On this page, the user will be able to make an inquiry per different filters:

- University
- Expertise (according to the list of ERC panels – see appendix 3)
- ENLIGHT flagships (see list appendix 3)
- Key words

As detailed above, we started with a pilot phase with four universities to be able to collect all the data on time for the delivery of the R&I observatory. The data of the remaining five universities will be integrated in 2023.

Through this search, users will have access to basic information related to research units (departments/groups...) of the Alliance.

The information provided for each research unit includes:

- Name of the research unit/group
- Description
- Expertise
- Subthematics
- Flagship domains
- Keywords
- Website

2.3. ENLIGHT Outputs

On this page, users will have access to the outputs of other ENLIGHT RISE Work packages' tasks. This section is organized per main thematic of ENLIGHT RISE.

Not all ENLIGHT RISE results or deliverables will be published on the R&I observatory. This will be discussed within WP2 and with other WPs teams. It will depend on the nature and content of the output.

The outputs page will be updated each time a result of an ENLIGHT RISE work package is finalised and becomes available to be published.

Research & Innovation Synergies

Mapping of scientific and technological domains and common skills
 This report explores and applies a technology intelligence-based approach to map the R&I activities of the nine universities of the ENLIGHT alliance based on a set of selected scientific and technological data associated with them.
[See details](#)

Digital research infrastructures

Mapping of Digital Research Infrastructural Resources

The report brings together a mapping of Digital Research Infrastructural Resources across ENLIGHT RISE partners. A mapping exercise aims at creating an overview of platforms, competences and priorities within the ENLIGHT community. The objective is to identify synergies related to the ENLIGHT flagship areas and provide input for future joint R/I actions. A roadmap for connecting and sharing digital infrastructural resources between the nine partner universities is outlined. Preparations for future digital alignment of innovation ecosystems and a responsible use of AI are also discussed.

[See details](#)

Research assessment & Early Career Researchers

The Evaluation of Research and Researchers. Current trends and developments

ENLIGHT RISE partners explore how the current debate impacts the evaluation systems of individual universities and what it might mean for the ENLIGHT European University. This background document is a starting point for all those involved in the assessment of research and researchers – policy makers, research support staff and researchers involved in the design and implementation of research(er) assessment systems – to plunge into the current debate and its implications.

[See details](#)

Open Science

ENLIGHT Open Science Status Quo & Opportunities

Mapping of Open Science (OS) activities across the ENLIGHT university alliance through an Open Science Status Matrix. It highlights good practices, identifies gaps and opportunities for joint action, proposes joint principles, and outlines options for rewards and incentives.

[See details](#)

Research Impact

Web-based repository and tool for mutual learning on R&I Impact

A web-based tool which acts as a repository of international good practices on research impact assessment and measurement.

[See details](#)

Innovation

Map of academy-industry partnerships

To be published on Jan. 2023

[See details](#)

CONCLUSION

The web-based tool of ENLIGHT R&I observatory was published on December 14th, 2022 at the following link

<https://observatory.enlight-eu.org>

It is accessible through the ENLIGHT website, at the [Research & Innovation](#) tab and will be disseminated through ENLIGHT communication tools and channels.

The ENLIGHT R&I Observatory is open to the overall public and some sections will be updated on a regular basis notably to include the ENLIGHT outputs, integrate the research capacities data of the five remaining universities and update those data for all when needed (once a year).

Appendix 1 - R&I observatory survey

ENLIGHT RISE *Research & Innovation with and for Society*

Deliverable 2.2_ R&I Observatory

Task 2.2. Creation of an ENLIGHT R&I observatory

We will set up an ENLIGHT R&I Observatory as an online one-stop shop portal centralizing various benchmarking results, surveys, and evidence-based policy recommendations emerging from the project (e.g. from Task 2.1, see also references to the Observatory in other WPs). The Observatory will be connected to the ENLIGHT website and will be designed for a broad audience of researchers and (for non-confidential sections) also to non-academic stakeholders of ENLIGHT. It will connect the R&I capability of the network strongly to the local, regional, city initiatives within ENLIGHT, serving as a tool for developing strategy based on the return from the “quadruple helix” instruments of ENLIGHT. The ENLIGHT R&I Observatory will be a key tool for designing a dynamic common R&I agenda with and for society. It will be a central resource for the R&I-SG, the Think Tank, Living Labs, and Regional Academies to identify emerging topics and generate cross-disciplinary, relevant research synergies in a competitive way. A central validation process by the ENLIGHT project board prior to posting information on the Observatory will be established.

In order to have a basis for our upcoming brainstorm on the R&I observatory, we invite each university to provide feedback on its expertise on observatories and on its expectations for the ENLIGHT R&I observatory.

Expertise/experience in Observatories

- What experience do you have locally with an observatory (any observatory, any topic)? Please detail

- Is there a particular expertise within your university in the implementation of an observatory? Please detail

Research Data System

- Is there a Research Data System within your university?

○ How it is deployed ? structured?

○ How are your research data listed?

ENLIGHT R&I Observatory

- What do you expect from the R&I observatory?

- According to you, what functions/sections shall it get?

- What kind of data shall it store?

- Who shall be the target group of the R&I observatory?

Appendix 3 – Lists of expertise & ENLIGHT Flagship domains

1. List of expertise (Panel structure for ERC calls 2021 and 2022)

Mathematics

Fundamental_constituents_of_Matter

Condensed_matter_physics

Physical_and_analytical_chemical_sciences

Synthetic_chemistry_and_materials

Computer_science_and_Informatics

Systems_and_communication_engineering

Products_and_processes_engineering

Universe_sciences

Earth_System_Science

Materials_engineering

Molecules_of_life_biological_mechanisms_structures_and_functions

Integrative_Biology_from_genes_and_genomes_to_systems

Cellular_developmental_and_regenerative_biology

Physiology_in_Health_Disease_and_Ageing

Neuroscience_and_disorders_of_the_nervous_system

Immunity_Infection_and_Immunotherapy

Prevention_Diagnosis_Treatment_of_Human_Diseases

Environmental_Biology_Ecology_and_Evolution

Biotechnology_and_Biosystems_Engineering

Individuals_Markets_and_Organisations

Institutions_Governance_and_Legal_Systems

The_Social_World_and_Its_Diversity

The_Human_Mind_and_Its_Complexity

Cultures_and_Cultural_Production

The_Study_of_the_Human_Past

Human_Mobility_Environment_and_Space

2. List of ENLIGHT flagship domains

Health & Well-Being

Energy and Circular Economy

Climate Change

Digital Revolution and Impact of Digitization

Equity

Other